

Thermodynamic study of polymersurfactant interaction in aqueous system

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Abstract : The critical micellar concentrations (CMC) of sodium dedecyl sulfate (SDS) in aqueous poly(vinyl pyrrodine) (PVP) (M.W. 40000) solutions have been determined at different temperatures. The CMC of SDS increases with increase in concentration of PVP and decrease with increase of temperature. The critical aggregation concentration (CAC) and polymer saturation point (PSP) decrease with increase in temperature. The effect of the increase in polymer concentration of CAC and PSP has been determined. The thermodynamic quantities associated with the PSP are computed.

Keywords : Thermodynamic study, polymer surfactant, micellar concentration.

Studies of the interaction between nonionic, water-soluble polymers and micelles have their roots in biochemistry, for they originated from the study of protein-surfactant interactions¹. Here we report the effect of polymer concentration of poly(vinyl pyrrodine) (PVP) in aqueous systems on critical micellar concentrations (CMC) of the sodium dedecyl sulfate (SDS) at different temperatures.

Results and discussion

The plots of specific conductance (k) versus surfactant concentration for the systems in various polymer solutions have been given in Fig. 1. These plots exhibit three regions, below the critical aggregation concentration (CAC), between the CAC and polymer saturation point (PSP) and above the PSP where micelle like aggregates develop and the third one is above the PSP where co-existence of dynamic equilibrium of surfactant saturated polymer and regular micelles² occur. Two remarks must be made concerning the CAC and PSP. First, the term CAC refers to the onset of mixed micelle formation between polymer and surfactant, and there is no more significance attached to it than in the case of mixed micellization between a surfactant and any additive, a polymer, for instance. Secondly, contrary to general notion³, the concentration of PSP does not correspond to the concentration of saturation of the polymer. The CMC values for SDS in presence of polymer (PVP) in aqueous media are included in Table 1. It is observed that as temperature rises, the CMC value decrease indicating that the micellization is favoured in the system. The CMC values increase with increase in the polymer concentration due to the availability of more and more reactive binding sites; hence more surfactant is needed for micellization. It is well known⁴ that the micellar structure may be considered to be made up of two regions, an outer region comprising polar head groups plus a portion of hydrocarbon chains in contact with and an inner region, (the hydrocarbon core) containing only the remaining hydrocarbon chain without any water molecule.

Fig. 1. Plots of specific conductance (k) vs concentration of SDS in presence of 0.001 % of PVP at different temperatures in water.

Table 1. The values of critical micellar concentration (CMC), the standard values of free energy of micellization (ΔG_{mic}°), enthalpy of micellization (ΔH_{mic}°), entropy of micellization (ΔS_{mic}°), and free energy transfer of micellization (ΔG_{tr}°) of SDS in presence of different percentages of PVP and at different temperatures in water

%PVP (w/v)	Temp. (°C)	CMC (mM)	$(-\Delta G_{mic}^{\circ})$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_{mic}° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS_{mic}° (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	$(-\Delta G_{tr}^{\circ})$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
0.0	30	8.79	21.4	7.1	94	-
	35	8.26	22.1	17.3	128	-
	40	7.60	22.8	24.7	150	-
	45	7.01	23.3	40.2	202	-
0.0001	30	11.11	38.5	16.1	180	1.06
	35	10.40	39.5	16.7	182	1.06
	40	9.60	40.5	17.2	184	1.09
	45	8.02	42.0	17.8	188	0.64
0.001	30	12.51	38.0	14.1	172	1.60
	35	11.85	38.9	14.6	173	1.66
	40	10.93	39.9	15.1	175	1.70
	45	10.46	40.7	15.6	177	1.90
0.002	30	13.58	37.6	11.7	162	1.97
	35	12.77	38.5	12.1	164	2.00
	40	11.78	39.5	12.5	166	2.05
	45	10.80	40.6	12.9	168	2.05
0.003	30	14.21	37.4	10.4	158	2.17
	35	13.25	38.4	10.8	159	2.17
	40	12.60	39.8	11.8	162	2.36
	45	11.50	40.2	11.5	162	2.35

Thermodynamic parameters :

The standard free energy of micellization (ΔG_{mic}°) for the systems studied were calculated using the relations^{5,6}

$$\Delta G_{mic}^{\circ} = (2 - P/n) RT \ln (\text{CMC}) \quad (1)$$

where, P = number of residual charges per micelle, n = micellar aggregation number.

For ionic surfactants $P/n = 0.2$ in aqueous solution. Here, CMC is taken in the mole fraction scale⁵. The values of enthalpy of micellization (ΔH_{mic}°) and the entropy of micellization (ΔS_{mic}°) were calculated using the relation⁶

$$\Delta H_{mic}^{\circ} = -RT^2 \delta \ln (\text{CMC})/\delta T \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta S_{mic}^{\circ} = \frac{\Delta H_{mic}^{\circ} - \Delta G_{mic}^{\circ}}{T} \quad (3)$$

To calculate the ΔH_{mic}° , $\ln (\text{CMC})$ is plotted against T and the slope of the straight line is taken as $\delta \ln (\text{CMC})/\delta T$. The ΔG_{mic}° , ΔH_{mic}° and ΔS_{mic}° values are presented in Table 1. The ΔG_{mic}° values were found to be negative, indicating a spontaneous micellization process⁷. A decrease in negative values is observed with increase in polymer concentration, indicating the increase in the hydrophobic interactions that leads to an increase in the

ΔG_{mic}° and the CMC values. The enthalpy of micellization (ΔH_{mic}°) are positive and are found to increase with temperature for the polymers (PVP). This indicates the overall micellization process was found to be endothermic. The enthalpy of micellization consists of SDS-SDS interactions, polymer-SDS interactions, and polymer-polymer interactions. These interactions may be broken down into a hydrophobic portion as well as an electrostatic contribution due to the mixing of the surfactant, and polymers in the head group region of the micelle. The ΔS_{mic}° values for all the systems studied were fairly positive, indicating that the micellization process is entropy dominated, particularly when the entropy change is high which is generally associated with phase changes and the increase in entropy due to water structure breakdown on micellization as well as due to release of water molecules associated with hydrocarbon chains⁸, which overshadows the decrease in entropy due to the micelle formation.

On plotting enthalpy vs entropy changes (Fig. 2) at various polymer concentrations, a linear correlation is obtained. The slope of the straight line in degrees have been computed and they are 299.56 K for SDS/PEG and 256.64 K for SDS-PVP, which are not far from the suggested literature value for water 270–294 K⁹. This im-

plies that the phenomena of micellization are governed by the bulk structural property of the solvent not only in water but also in solvent-polymer solutions. This indi-

Fig. 2. The plots of ΔH°_{mic} and ΔS°_{mic} for the system of SDS and PVP in water.

cates that the polymer surfactant interactions in this condition depends only upon the entropy change. Such enthalpy-entropy compensation effects were observed earlier in many physico-chemical process¹⁰.

The standard free energy values of transfer (ΔG°_{tr}) of the surfactant (SDS) for the aqueous polymer solutions of the polymer-water solution are calculated using the relation⁵

$$\Delta G^{\circ}_{tr} = (2 - P/n) RT \ln \frac{CMC}{CMC^*} + (2 - P/n) RT \ln \frac{f}{f^*} \quad (4)$$

where CMC and f represents the critical micelle concentration and the activity coefficient of surfactant respectively in water. CMC^* and f^* are values corresponding to polymer and surfactant system. As the surfactant concentrations in the systems studied are very low, therefore, f/f^* value, has been taken as unity. The ΔG°_{tr} values are presented in Table 1. The results shows that the ΔG°_{tr} values (Table 1) for the system are negative and increase with increase in temperature and also with the increase in polymer concentration indicating the more feasibility of the transfer of SDS micelles from aqueous media to aqueous polymer media¹¹.

Experimental

The sodium dedecyl sulfate salt (Aldrich, England) (SDS) used in measurements was recrystallized from the mixture of ethanol/benzene (1 : 1 volume), and then the precipitated surfactant was washed by acetone, dried under vacuum at room temperature, and kept in a desiccator above dried $CaSO_4$. Poly(vinyl pyrrolidone) (PVP) (M. W. 40000) was purified by fractionation, followed by deionization. PVP was dissolved in chloroform and precipitated in ether. Aqueous solutions (50% w/w) of the respective precipitate were deionized by stirring with cationic and anionic ion-exchange material until the specific conductivities of the solutions were below $10 \mu \Omega^{-1} cm^{-1}$. The deionized solutions were dialyzed against demineralized water in cellulose acetate tubes for 25 h. The conductance of the solutions were measured using a direct reading electronic display conductometer [Elico Limited, Hyderabad], which was calibrated using standard KCl solution before making the measurements. The conductance values were measured, the concentration of the solution varied by adding aliquots of concentrated stock solution to the known volume of the solution in the jacketed vessel with the help of a micro syringe. All measurements were carried out at a constant temperature controlled thermostat working with a precession of $\pm 0.005^{\circ}$.

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